

Leveraging the molecular complexity of lignin for high-performance bio-based materials

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Lignin forms the polyphenolic network in wood that enables trees to stand upright, transport water and ions, and resist microbial attack. Although its structural complexity is often seen as a limitation, its inherent multifunctionality offers opportunities. By strategically harnessing these features, new directions for advanced lignin-based materials can emerge.

Foundational challenges of lignin as a macromolecular raw material

Lignin has long been regarded as a problematic raw material, combining the absence of a crystalline structure with high brittleness, low mechanical strength, a dark color, residual impurities, and often an unpleasant odor. In many respects, it has been easier to list unattractive features than to enumerate properties that would motivate the use of lignin for high-performance materials. Nevertheless, once largely regarded as a low-value by-product of the pulp and paper industry, various types of lignin are now increasingly recognized as among the most promising feedstocks for bio-based materials.

The rise of colloidal lignin particles as uniform building blocks

During the last decade, our understanding of the multifaceted aspects of lignin has considerably progressed. The rise of lignin nanoparticles has been one of the main transformative drivers in

this field. Lignin nanoparticles offer a way to circumvent the intrinsic molecular complexity of heterogeneous lignin macromolecules, which exhibit broad size and polarity distributions. This “standardization,” enabled by colloidally stable lignin particle dispersions, has provided a platform for multifaceted research, leading to startup companies and a wide range of applications, including functional fillers in nanocomposites, adhesives, coatings, emulsifiers, and structural colors (**Figure 1**). As it turned out, these lignin particles also came to play a central role in my research.

Figure 1. Past, present and possible future research directions on lignin nanoparticles and related materials. The figure shows that lignin nanoparticles have been a major research area over the past decade, enabling the entry of lignin into new applications. While this field continues to flourish, a future perspective is to consider molecular diversity in greater detail when developing new high-performance materials designed for circularity. Another dimension is the growing influence of multidisciplinary research and collaboration across fields.

Catching the colloidal lignin wave

Transitioning from industrially driven research on lignocellulosic biorefinery development to lignin-based functional materials, I had the privilege of being at the forefront of the emerging research on colloidal lignin particles when I began my postdoctoral work in 2016. At that time, several open questions remained regarding particle formation and stability, particularly in relation to lignin structure and process parameters. I first recognized the potential of colloidal

lignin particles while working in the group of Prof. Monika Österberg, through their pioneering work.¹ During this postdoctoral period, I also benefited from mentorship by Dr. Heiko Lange in the group of Prof. Claudia Crestini, where we combined our interests in particle formation mechanisms with active substance encapsulation and controlled release. Our work showed that the particle formation mechanism is driven by gradual changes in lignin solubility, which are in turn affected by molecular weight and polarity, allowing a gradient-type buildup of the particles, with relatively more hydrophobic molecules embedded inside and the most hydrophilic ones residing at the surface.²

Equally important for my career development was working in a junior faculty position alongside ambitious early-career researchers. In this regard, the initial momentum for establishing my group was largely thanks to Dr. Adrian Moreno, my first group member and now a tenure-track faculty in Spain. Our work built on an amalgamation of polymer chemistry and materials chemistry, resulting in the development of hypothesis-driven enzyme-assisted emulsion polymerization chemistries,³ and in both rational design⁴ and serendipitous discoveries⁵ related to lignin nanoparticle stability and functionalization. I have also witnessed the rise of several subfields, such as lignin nanoparticle-based platforms for enzyme immobilization, which has become a lively research area of its own with potential applications including phospholipid modification⁶ and aqueous esterification reactions.⁷

Harnessing the molecular diversity of lignin

Frontier research on lignin is increasingly shaped by interdisciplinary and collaborative efforts across fields such as materials chemistry, engineering, biotechnology and computational chemistry, with growing influence from the three pillars of sustainability: environmental, economic, and social. Rather than seeking to replicate petrochemical polymers, lignin's inherent properties, including structural diversity, hierarchical organization, and selective reactivity, can be deliberately harnessed. My vision for the future is to combine molecular-level

structural insights with supramolecular materials design, including, but not limited to, lignin nanoparticles. Intrinsic features such as three-dimensional branching and tunable aggregation behavior open new pathways for mesoscale structural control, stimuli-responsiveness, and hybrid materials design (**Fig. 1**). Catalysis and active-substance delivery are clear examples of applications in which mesoscale control of lignin can considerably enhance performance through the tailoring of porosity and surface area. Harnessing lignin macromolecular attributes, such as tunable molar mass distribution, polarity, and chain rigidity is central not only for controlling lignin aggregation,⁸ but also for enabling molecular-scale interactions with other organic and inorganic substances. Moreover, considering the entire lifecycle of lignin-based materials provides a strong rationale for advanced materials design. Materials derived from lignin can be engineered to evolve during use, adapting to moisture, pH, heat, or mechanical stress in ways that echo how the native lignin network evolves in wood.

While recognizing the breadth of lignin's molar-mass and polarity distributions, opportunities emerge to alter the structural features of lignin populations through a deeper understanding of lignin's structure and morphology in native biomass, coupled with tailored extraction and chemical functionalization strategies. Together, these strategies allows tuning of material properties, as exemplified by lignin-derived carbon fibers, where differences in lignin source translate into variations in chemical composition and interunit linkage distribution, dictating the resulting fiber performance.⁹ Similarly, selected softwood kraft lignin fractions, sequentially modified with ethylene carbonate and benzoic acid, have been used as toughening additives in commodity plastics, demonstrating lignin's potential as a functional additive.¹⁰ In addition to establishing predictable structure–property relationships, developing strategies for preserving the extended macromolecular chains through selective extraction processes may help overcome longstanding issues in lignin's polymer properties such as its inherent brittleness. Materials chemistry and engineering of lignin should be supported by computational

and data-driven methods, with emphasis on discovery of new functionalities and enhanced performance.

Beyond molecular design, the manufacturing, formulation, and processing of sustainable lignin-based products relies on close collaboration between academia, spin-offs, and industry. Translational research and multi-stakeholder partnerships can unlock substantial benefits, prioritizing design for circularity, biodegradability, and lifecycle engineering to align lignin-based materials with sustainable development goals.

Outlook

Although substantial efforts have focused on isolating narrow molar-mass fractions and small aromatic compounds from lignin through chemical and engineering approaches, future advances may lie with those willing to embrace its intrinsic heterogeneity rather than eliminate it. Lignin represents a versatile macromolecular platform whose structural diversity should be regarded not as a limitation, but as a source of functionality. In this sense, progress will require shifting from an emphasis on compositional uniformity toward purposeful use of lignin's inherent complexity. The central challenge, therefore, is to develop materials that do not require rendering lignin into a standardized commodity, but instead harness its molecular diversity through new design principles. Viewed in this way, lignin becomes a source of macromolecules capable of inspiring materials that evolve, store history, and respond to stimuli throughout their lifetime, rather than serving merely as a replacement for small molecules or conventional polymers. Embracing lignin in this role invites a broader rethinking of how its complexity and multifunctionality can benefit the design of materials with unique chemical fingerprints that are not readily available from fossil-derived synthetic options.

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Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.